

Uncovering the Citation Landscape: Exploring OpenCitations COCI, OpenCitations Meta, and ERIH-PLUS in Social Sciences and Humanities Journals

Version 6

Description

Purpose

The main purpose of this research is to answer to three different questions and find out:

1. the number of citations which refer to publications in Social Sciences and Humanities journals included in ERIH-PLUS, by looking at citations data contained in OpenCitations COCI and OpenCitations Meta;
2. the most citing and the most cited SSH discipline, according to the above mentioned datasets;
3. the citations coming from and going to publications contained in OpenCitations Meta which are not included in SSH journals.

Methodology

We want to draw a line that connects these three different datasets, aiming at offering an overall view of the citations landscape of each of them. For this purpose, we approach the problem from a computational point of view. We extract only the relevant data by operating a first preprocessing of COCI, ERIH-PLUS and META's datasets. Then we build a python software able to analyze CSVs data, querying them to retrieve information needed and to present the results in a clear and understandable way.

Findings

The findings show that the majority of citations come from and go to psychology publications, and a deep gap exists between the number of citations included in SSH journals and the number of citations that are not included in SSH journals.

Originality/Value

The research conducted by us has the purpose to add information to existing resources with the aim of facilitating their use and allowing the researchers to have a clearer view of the data contained in each dataset. In addition, the research has the purpose to gather information that may be useful for understanding which is the most influential discipline in the SSH field and to provide a solid starting point for further studies regarding this subject.

Keywords: COCI, Meta, ERIH-PLUS, OpenCitations, SSH, Journals

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Researchers

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Organizations

University of Bologna

Datasets

Title: [Pika.py Dataset](#)

Template: [Horizon 2020](#)

The dataset obtained from the processing of the 3rd version OpenCitations Meta (OpenCitations, 2023), the 19th version OpenCitations COCI (OpenCitations, 2023) and the version of 27/04/23 of ERIH-PLUS (ErihPlus, 2023) datasets, which have been filtered and cleaned keeping only the relevant data needed for the purpose of the research. The dataset produced is composed by different files which serve the purpose of answering to the three research questions.

Dataset Description

1.1 Data Summary

[1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?](#)

- To obtain information
- To share information
- To combine with other data

With this dataset we want to obtain specific information about the number of citations retrieved from OpenCitations COCI that involve publications in SSH Journals included in OpenCitations Meta. In addition, we want to have some insights about the disciplines citing and cited the most. Lastly, we want to highlight the number of citations starting from and pointing to publications in OpenCitations Meta, not included in SSH Journals.

[1.1.2 What are the types of the described generated/collected data?](#)

- sample or specimen data
- derived or compiled (e.g.
- text mining
- 3D models)

According to what we said above, our data are secondary data about citations retrieved from the three previously mentioned open source datasets (COCI, Meta, ERIH-PLUS).

1.1.3 What are the formats of the described generated/collected data?

- Text files
- Discipline specific formats

The format of our dataset is CSV.

1.1.4 What is the origin of the described data?

Secondary data

1.1.5 What is the expected size of the described data?

GB (gigabyte)

We expect that our dataset will have GB size, since COCI is 37.4 GB (in zip format), Meta is 8 GB (in zip format).

1.1.6 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Education

Experts in the field of SSH

Open Science researches

Academics

2.1 Reused Data

2.1.1 Are you re-using the described data and how?

Yes

- To compare and combine with other data
- To develop new products/ services

2.1.2 Where do the described data reside?

a. figshare

b. <https://kanalregister.hkdir.no/publiseringskanaler/erihplus/periodical/listApproved>

2.1.3 Which data will be re-used?

a. <https://kanalregister.hkdir.no/publiseringskanaler/erihplus/periodical/listApproved> (For what concerns EIRH-PLUS, we have noticed that "print ISSN" and "online ISSN" correspond to the "venue" column of META, thus we have kept these two columns (unified into one single column) and the ERIH PLUS Disciplines column, too).

b. [OpenCitations Meta CSV dataset of all bibliographic metadata](#)

we have used the following columns (all the original columns): "id", "title", "author", "issue", "volume", "venue", "page", "pub_date", "type", "publisher", "editor". Here the link to the Meta dataset 3rd version: <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.21747461.v3>

c. [COCI CSV dataset of all the citation data](#)

we have kept the COCI columns "citing" and "cited", because they were corresponding to DOIs, which are contained also in the "id" column of META. Here the link to the Meta dataset 19th version: <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.6741422.v19>

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 Will you use metadata to describe the data?

No

We use keywords on Zenodo to provide information about the data published. We don't use a metadata schema for the description of our dataset.

3.1.1.3 Will your metadata use standardised vocabularies?

No

3.1.1.5 Will you make the metadata available free-of-charge?

Data will be available to download from Zenodo.

3.1.1.7 Will you use naming conventions for your data?

Yes

3.1.1.8 Please provide more details and examples on used naming conversions

a. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Snake_case

snake_case

b. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Camel_case

camelCase

3.1.1.9 Will you provide clear version numbers for your data?

Yes

We use the versioning system provided by Zenodo (each DOIs correspond to a different version, e.g. Version 1, Version 2 and so on).

3.1.1.10 Will you provide persistent identifiers for the described data?

Yes

3.1.1.11 Persistent identifiers

DOI

3.1.1.12 Will you provide searchable metadata for the described data?

Yes

size, Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs), ORCID.

3.1.1.13 What services will you use to provide searchable metadata?

Other

We don't make use of searchable metadata. We use the Zenodo automatic cataloging for the publications based on the Keywords provided.

3.1.1.15 Will you use standardised formats for the described data?

Yes

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

3.1.1.16 Provide information about used standardised formats

<https://www.ietf.org/>

csv, RFC 4180

3.1.1.18 Are the file formats you will use open?

Yes

3.1.1.20 Do supported open-source tools exist for accessing the data?

Yes

3.1.1.22 Will you provide metadata describing the quality of the data?

No

3.1.2 Making data openly accessible

3.1.2.1 Are there ethical or legal issues that can impact sharing the described data?

No

3.1.2.2 Will the described data be openly accessible?

Yes

3.1.2.3 How will the data be made available?

Other

Github repository, Zenodo

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

3.1.2.4 Please provide URL/Name of used data repositories

<https://zenodo.org/>

Zenodo

3.1.2.5 Is the storage sufficiently secure for the data and does the storage provide backup and recovery procedures?

secure with backup and recovery

For what concerns backup and recovery, all files uploaded to Zenodo are stored in CERN's EOS service. Each file copy has two replicas located on different disk servers. The other checksum is stored by EOS, and used for automatic detection and recovery of file corruption on disks.

3.1.2.6 Are there any methods or tools required to access the described data?

No

3.1.2.9 Will you also make auxiliary data that may be of interest to researchers available?

no auxiliary data

3.1.3 Making data interoperable

3.1.3.1 Will you use a controlled vocabulary for the described data?

No

3.1.3.2 Will you provide a mapping to more commonly used ontologies?

no

3.1.4 Increase data reuse

3.1.4.1 When do you plan to make the described data available for reuse?

immediately

3.1.4.4 What internationally recognised licence(s) will you use for the described data?

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International

3.1.4.5 Do you have documented procedures for quality assurance of the described data?

No

3.1.4.8 Will you provide any support for data reuse?

Yes

protocol.io for describing our workflow and we will make available all the data used and produced in our research

3.1.4.9 How long do you intend to support data reuse?

More than 10 years

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 How will the cost of making the described data findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable be covered?

Infrastructure Grant

University of Bologna

4.1.2 Will you identify a data manager to manage the described data? If not who will be responsible for the management of the data?

Yes

Olga Pagnotta, Marta Soricetti, Sara Vellone, Lorenzo Paolini

4.1.3 Identify the people or roles that will be responsible for the management of the described data

a. Olga Pagnotta (orcid:0009-0004-5901-5730)

manager and developer

b. Marta Soricetti (orcid:0009-0008-1466-7742)

manager and developer

c. Sara Vellone (orcid:0009-0008-4037-6607)

manager and developer

d. Lorenzo Paolini (orcid:0009-0003-3803-4011)

manager and developer

4.1.4 How do you intend to ensure data reuse after your project finishes?

- Other
- Personal Archive

Zenodo and Github

protocol.io for describing our workflow and we will make available all the data used and produced in our research both on Zenodo and our personal Github repository.

5.1 Data Security

5.1.1 Where do you plan to keep the described data?

Kept on secure, managed storage for limited time

Github and Zenodo

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing?

No

6.1.2 Are the described data sensitive?

No

6.1.3 Are the described data personal?

No

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

Title: [Pika.py software](#)

Template: [Horizon 2020](#)

This is the dataset for the python software we have created for the research purpose. With this software we provide the answer to the research questions (see DMP description). We used it to preprocess the original datasets, to create our new datasets and to provide the proper answers.

Dataset Description

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?

- To obtain information
- To share information
- To combine with other data

We have cross-analysed three different datasets (COCI, META, ERIH-PLUS) in order to gather specific information about SSH journals Citations and other disciplines. The software will process the datasets, filter and clean them and extract the needed information.

1.1.2 What are the types of the described generated/collected data?

- sample or specimen data
- derived or compiled (e.g.
- text mining
- 3D models)

We are dealing with bibliographic data, in particular citations data.

1.1.3 What are the formats of the described generated/collected data?

Software

the software is developed in python

1.1.4 What is the origin of the described data?

Primary data

1.1.5 What is the expected size of the described data?

MB (megabyte)

1.1.6 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Education
- The public

2.1 Reused Data

2.1.1 Are you re-using the described data and how?

Yes

<https://github.com/opencitations/preprocess>

To develop new products/ services

2.1.2 Where do the described data reside?

GitHub

<https://github.com/opencitations/preprocess>

2.1.3 Which data will be re-used?

We have used the splitted_to_file and split_input methods
(<https://github.com/opencitations/preprocess>)

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 Will you use metadata to describe the data?

No

We use keywords on Zenodo to provide information about the data published. We don't use a metadata schema for the description of our dataset.

3.1.1.3 Will your metadata use standardised vocabularies?

No

3.1.1.5 Will you make the metadata available free-of-charge?

Zenodo and Github

3.1.1.6 Will your metadata be harvestable?

Zenodo and Github

3.1.1.7 Will you use naming conventions for your data?

Yes

3.1.1.8 Please provide more details and examples on used naming conversions

a. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Snake_case

snake_case

b. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Camel_case

camelCase

3.1.1.9 Will you provide clear version numbers for your data?

Yes

We have used the versioning system provided by Github through the use of tags, e.g. v1.0.0.

3.1.1.10 Will you provide persistent identifiers for the described data?

Yes

doi

3.1.1.11 Persistent identifiers

DOI

3.1.1.12 Will you provide searchable metadata for the described data?

No

3.1.1.15 Will you use standardised formats for the described data?

Yes

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

3.1.1.16 Provide information about used standardised formats

a. <https://www.python.org/>

python (.py)

3.1.1.18 Are the file formats you will use open?

Yes

3.1.1.20 Do supported open-source tools exist for accessing the data?

No

3.1.1.22 Will you provide metadata describing the quality of the data?

No

3.1.2 Making data openly accessible

3.1.2.1 Are there ethical or legal issues that can impact sharing the described data?

No

3.1.2.2 Will the described data be openly accessible?

Yes

3.1.2.3 How will the data be made available?

Other

Github and Zenodo

Github repository for the software: <https://github.com/open-sci/2022-2023-pika-py-code.git>

Zenodo: <https://zenodo.org/badge/latestdoi/627425384>

3.1.2.5 Is the storage sufficiently secure for the data and does the storage provide backup and recovery procedures?

secure with backup and recovery

For what concerns backup and recovery, all files uploaded to Zenodo are stored in CERN's

EOS service. Each file copy has two replicas located on different disk servers.

The other checksum is stored by EOS, and used for automatic detection and

recovery of file corruption on disks.

In addition, Github allows for the recovering of data if they have been deleted, and allows for backup through the history of changes made in the repository.

3.1.2.6 Are there any methods or tools required to access the described data?

No

3.1.2.9 Will you also make auxiliary data that may be of interest to researchers available?

no auxiliary data

3.1.3 Making data interoperable

3.1.3.1 Will you use a controlled vocabulary for the described data?

No

3.1.3.2 Will you provide a mapping to more commonly used ontologies?

No

3.1.4 Increase data reuse

3.1.4.1 When do you plan to make the described data available for reuse?

immediately

3.1.4.4 What internationally recognised licence(s) will you use for the described data?

ISC License

ISC license

3.1.4.5 Do you have documented procedures for quality assurance of the described data?

Yes

3.1.4.7 Describe the data quality assurance processes

Not available

we have devised two different softwares for offering to the user the possibility to choose if to produce output files or not but also for checking the correctness of the answers and the soundness of the software itself.

3.1.4.8 Will you provide any support for data reuse?

Yes

workflow (protocol.io) and methods description. Data used and produced are available for reproducibility purposes.

3.1.4.9 How long do you intend to support data reuse?

Up to 5 years

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 How will the cost of making the described data findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable be covered?

Use of institution infrastructure

University of Bologna

4.1.2 Will you identify a data manager to manage the described data? If not who will be responsible for the management of the data?

Yes

4.1.3 Identify the people or roles that will be responsible for the management of the described data

a. Olga Pagnotta (orcid:0009-0004-5901-5730)

Developer and Owner

b. Marta Soricetti (orcid:0009-0008-1466-7742)

Developer and Owner

c. Sara Vellone (orcid:0009-0008-4037-6607)

Developer and Owner

d. Lorenzo Paolini (orcid:0009-0003-3803-4011)

Developer and Owner

4.1.4 How do you intend to ensure data reuse after your project finishes?

- Institutional archive
- Other
- Personal Archive

zenodo

workflow (protocol.io) and methods description. Data used and produced are available for reproducibility purposes.

5.1 Data Security

5.1.1 Where do you plan to keep the described data?

Kept on secure, managed storage for limited time

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing?

No

6.1.2 Are the described data sensitive?

No

6.1.3 Are the described data personal?

No

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

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